

An Analysis of Enrolment of Women at Undergraduate level in Arunachal Pradesh

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Abstract:

The present paper examines the pattern of enrolment of women at undergraduate level in Arunachal Pradesh with special reference to Papum Pare, Tirap and Lohit districts during the academic sessions 2021-22 to 2023-24. Data collected from selected government colleges and Directorate of Higher and Technical Education (DHTE), the study analyses district-wise and stream-wise enrolment of women at undergraduate level. The findings reveal an overall positive trend in enrolment of women at undergraduate level, particularly in Papum Pare and Lohit, while Tirap district shows fluctuations over the period under study. At the stream level, Humanities continues to dominate enrollment, whereas science shows stagnation and commerce reflects fluctuating participation. Although the total enrollment of women at the state level remains relatively stable with minor variations, regional disparities persist, indicating the need for targeted policy interventions to ensure balanced growth of women's participation in higher education level across districts and streams.

Keywords: Enrolment, Undergraduate Level, Arunachal Pradesh, District-wise analysis, Stream-wise

1. Introduction

Education is a fundamental pillar of human society, serving as the cornerstone for individual and collective progress. As its core, education can be defined as the systematic process of acquiring knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes through various formal and informal means, such as schooling, training, and life experiences. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific Organization (UNESCO), education encompasses not only the transmission of information but also the cultivation of critical thinking, creativity, and ethical reasoning to foster holistic development. Throughout human progress, particularly in the contemporary era where the knowledge economy is favored by several nations, education serves as a crucial element and a catalyst for economic advancement. Education and training are not only essential for economic development, but they also contribute to socio-political stability and eventually, education and training contribute to boosting the human development index (Shust et al., 2022; Sele, J. P., & Mukundi, M. B. 2024). Research on economic growth has consistently acknowledged the significance of human capital and identified education as the principal means of its accumulation. Significant transformations in economic frameworks, sectors, and global labor markets have created a must for swift knowledge acquisition, alongside adaptability and job mobility for persons (Tyagi, A). The accumulation of information and technological advancement enhances individual workers' adaptability to new jobs. Consequently, integrated labor skills and competencies are essential prerequisites for workers to thrive in the contemporary workplace, attainable solely through education and training (Russ, M. 2017). Higher education represents the advanced stage of formal learning that builds upon foundational education, typically encompassing post-secondary programs offered by universities, colleges, technological institutes, and specialized institutions. It involves the pursuit of undergraduate, postgraduate, doctoral, and professional qualifications, where students engage in in-depth study, research, and skill specialization in chosen disciplines

Higher education plays a crucial role in empowering women and promoting social and economic development. In a state like Arunachal Pradesh, where geographical constraints, socio-cultural factors and infrastructural limitations influence educational access, participation of women in higher education assumes particular significance. Over the years, the Government of Arunachal Pradesh has undertaken several initiatives to improve women's access to higher education; however, disparities across districts and academic streams continue to exist.

The present study focuses on the enrolment of women at undergraduate level in Arunachal Pradesh, with specific emphasis on Papum Pare, Tirap and Lohit districts. By analyzing enrolment data, the paper attempts to understand emerging trends and patterns that can inform future educational planning and policy formulation.

2. Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the enrolment pattern of women at the undergraduate level in Papum Pare, Tirap and Lohit districts of Arunachal Pradesh from 2021-22 to 2023-24.
2. To examine stream-wise (humanities, science and commerce) enrolment of women at undergraduate level in Papum Pare, Tirap and Lohit districts of Arunachal Pradesh from 2021-22 to 2023-24.

3. Methodology

The study is descriptive in nature and based on the secondary data. The data relating to enrolment of women at undergraduate level for the academic sessions 2021-22, 2022-23 and 2023-24 were collected from the Academic Cells of Binni Yanga Government Women's College, Wangcha Rajkumar Government College and Indira Gandhi Government College and records from the Directorate of Higher and Technical Education (DHTE), Government of Arunachal Pradesh.

4. Analysis and Interpretation

Data collected from colleges and Directorate of Higher and Technical Education were analyzed and interpreted as per objectives of the study.

District-wise enrolment of women at undergraduate level in Papum Pare, Tirap and Lohit districts of Arunachal Pradesh from 2021-22 to 2023-24

Table 4.1: Showing enrolment of women at undergraduate level in Papum Pare, Tirap and Lohit districts of Arunachal Pradesh (2021–22 to 2023–24)

Academic Year	Papum Pare (No. of Students)	Tirap (No. of Students)	Lohit (No. of Students)	Total Female Enrolment in Arunachal Pradesh
2021–22	86	68	415	19,486
2022–23	120	48	388	18,410
2023–24	171	88	428	19,706

Source: Academic Cells of BYGWC, WRGC, and IGGC; Directorate of Higher and Technical Education (DHTE), Government of Arunachal Pradesh, Itanagar.

Fig 4.1 Showing enrolment of women at undergraduate level in Papum Pare, Tirap and Lohit districts of Arunachal Pradesh from 2021-22 to 2023-24.

The district-wise analysis shows a generally positive trend in enrolment of women in Papum Pare and Lohit districts. In Papum Pare, enrolment of women increased steadily from 86 students in 2021-22 to 171 students in 2023-24, reflecting a consistent rise in enrolment of women at the undergraduate level. Lohit district also recorded relatively high enrolment figures across all three academic years, with a slight decline in 2022-23 followed by an increase in 2023-24, indicating recovery and sustained interest among female students. In contrast, Tirap district exhibited a fluctuating trend. Enrolment declined from 68 students in 2021-22 to 48 students in 2022-23, but subsequently increased to 88 students in 2023-24. This uneven pattern may be attributed to factors such as accessibility issues, socio-cultural constraints or institutional limitations within the district. At the state level, enrolment of women at the undergraduate level remained relatively stable, with a marginal decline in 2022-23 and a slight improvement in 2023-24. This indicates a steady overall trend, though with minor deviations.

Showing stream-wise (humanities, science and commerce) enrolment of women at the undergraduate level in Papum Pare, Tirap and Lohit districts of Arunachal Pradesh from 2021-22 to 2023-24.

Table 4.2: Showing stream-wise (humanities, science and commerce) enrolment of women at undergraduate level in Papum Pare, Tirap and Lohit districts in different for the Academic Sessions 2021-22 to 2023-24

Academic Session	Humanities	Science	Commerce	Total Enrollment
2021-22	575	41	22	638
2022-23	568	40	29	637
2023-24	719	40	14	773

Fig 4.3: Showing stream-wise (humanities, science and commerce) enrolment of women at undergraduate level in Papum Pare, Tirap and Lohit districts of Arunachal Pradesh from 2021-22 to 2023-24.

The stream-wise analysis reveals that humanities consistently accounts for the highest enrolment of women across all three academic sessions. Enrolment in Humanities remained high in 2021-22 and 2022-23 and showed a significant increase in 2023-24, contributing substantially to the rise in total enrolment during that year. Enrolment in science among female students remained almost stagnant, with approximately 40-41 students enrolled across the three academic sessions. This suggests limited growth or capacity in science education for women. Enrolment in commerce enrolment showed a fluctuating pattern, with a rise in 2022-23 followed by a notable decline in 2023-24. Overall, the trend indicates a stronger preference for humanities, stable participation in science and inconsistent demand for Commerce courses among female students.

5. Conclusion

The study highlights a favorable trend in enrolment of women at higher education level in Arunachal Pradesh, particularly in Papum Pare and Lohit districts. However, the uneven distribution of enrolment across districts and academic streams underscores the need for targeted policy measures. Strengthening infrastructure, expanding Science and Commerce opportunities, and addressing district-specific barriers can help promote balanced growth in women's higher education. Ensuring equitable access and diversified academic options will be crucial for sustaining and enhancing female participation in higher education in the state.

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